

Supporting Information S1

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1 Geometric contour flows

In this section, we provide additional information on the curve-shortening flow (CSF), the area-preserving curve-shortening flow (APCSF) and the gradient flow of the area functional. For more details about the APCSF, see [1, 2].

Curve-shortening flow. The arc length of a contour Φ is given by the following functional

$$L(\Phi) = \int_0^{2\pi} \left\| \frac{\partial \Phi(\theta)}{\partial \theta} \right\|_2 d\theta.$$

In order to derive the corresponding gradient flow, we first deduce the following equality

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} L(\Phi) = \int_0^{2\pi} \frac{\frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial \theta}}{\left\| \frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial \theta} \right\|_2} \cdot \frac{\partial^2 \Phi}{\partial \theta \partial t} d\theta$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= \left[\frac{\frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial \theta}}{\left\| \frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial \theta} \right\|_2} \cdot \frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial t} \right]_0^{2\pi} - \int_0^{2\pi} \frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial t} \cdot \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} \left(\frac{\frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial \theta}}{\left\| \frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial \theta} \right\|_2} \right) d\theta \\
&= 0 - \int_0^{2\pi} \frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial t} \cdot \vec{t}' d\theta \\
&= - \int_0^{L(\Phi)} \frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial t} \cdot \frac{\vec{t}'}{\left\| \frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial \theta} \right\|_2} ds \\
&= - \int_0^{L(\Phi)} \frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial t} \cdot \kappa \vec{n}_{\text{inw}} ds
\end{aligned}$$

Hence, the most rapid decreasing of $L(\Phi)$ is given by

$$\frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial t} = \kappa \vec{n}_{\text{inw}}$$

which is known as the curve-shortening flow. The rate of the CSF is then given by

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial}{\partial t} L(\Phi) &= - \int_0^{L(\Phi)} \kappa^2 \|\vec{n}_{\text{inw}}\|_2^2 ds \\
&= - \int_0^{L(\Phi)} \kappa^2 ds,
\end{aligned}$$

where $\int_0^{L(\Phi)} \kappa^2 ds$ is called the total squared curvature.

Gradient flow of the area functional. As an alternative to the area-adjustment flow (AAF) from the main article, we propose the gradient flow of the area functional. First, we remind that the area of a contour Φ is given by the following functional

$$A(\Phi) = \int_0^{2\pi} \Phi^{(x)} d\Phi^{(y)} = \int_0^{2\pi} \Phi^{(x)} \frac{\partial \Phi^{(y)}}{\partial \theta} d\theta.$$

Then, the first variation of $A(\Phi)$ is given by

$$\begin{aligned}
\delta A(\Phi, h) &= \frac{d}{d\varepsilon} A(\Phi + \varepsilon h) \Big|_{\varepsilon=0} \\
&= \frac{d}{d\varepsilon} \int_0^{2\pi} (\Phi_x + \varepsilon h_x) \frac{\partial (\Phi_y + \varepsilon h_y)}{\partial \theta} d\theta \Big|_{\varepsilon=0} \\
&= \frac{d}{d\varepsilon} \int_0^{2\pi} (\Phi_x + \varepsilon h_x) \left(\frac{\partial \Phi_y}{\partial \theta} + \varepsilon \frac{\partial h_y}{\partial \theta} \right) d\theta \Big|_{\varepsilon=0} \\
&= \frac{d}{d\varepsilon} \int_0^{2\pi} \Phi_x \frac{\partial \Phi_y}{\partial \theta} + \varepsilon \Phi_x \frac{\partial h_y}{\partial \theta} + \varepsilon h_x \frac{\partial \Phi_y}{\partial \theta} + \varepsilon^2 h_x \frac{\partial h_y}{\partial \theta} d\theta \Big|_{\varepsilon=0} \\
&= \int_0^{2\pi} \Phi_x \frac{\partial h_y}{\partial \theta} + h_x \frac{\partial \Phi_y}{\partial \theta} d\theta
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= [\Phi_x h_y]_0^{2\pi} - \int_0^{2\pi} h_y \frac{\partial \Phi_x}{\partial \theta} d\theta + \int_0^{2\pi} h_x \frac{\partial \Phi_y}{\partial \theta} d\theta \\
&= \int_0^{2\pi} h_x \frac{\partial \Phi_y}{\partial \theta} - h_y \frac{\partial \Phi_x}{\partial \theta} d\theta \\
&= \int_0^{2\pi} \left\langle h, \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\partial \Phi_y}{\partial \theta} \\ -\frac{\partial \Phi_x}{\partial \theta} \end{pmatrix} \right\rangle d\theta = \int_0^{2\pi} \left\langle h, \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\partial \Phi_x}{\partial \theta} \\ \frac{\partial \Phi_y}{\partial \theta} \end{pmatrix}^\perp \right\rangle d\theta \\
&= \int_0^{L(\Phi)} \left\langle h, \frac{\left(\frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial \theta}\right)^\perp}{\left\|\frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial \theta}\right\|} \right\rangle ds = \int_0^{L(\Phi)} \langle h, \vec{t}^\perp \rangle ds \\
&= \int_0^{L(\Phi)} \langle h, \vec{n} \rangle ds
\end{aligned}$$

and therefore

$$\delta A(\Phi, h) = - \int_0^{L(\Phi)} \langle h, \vec{n}_{\text{inw}} \rangle ds \quad (1.1)$$

Now, for the direction $h = \frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial t} = \vec{n}_{\text{inw}}$, the area functional $A(\Phi)$ decreases most rapidly with the following rate:

$$\frac{\partial A(\Phi)}{\partial t} = - \int_0^{L(\Phi)} \|\vec{n}_{\text{inw}}\|_2^2 ds = -L(\Phi)$$

Similarly, we can compute the gradient flow of the following ‘‘area adjustment functional’’:

$$F(\Phi) := (A(\Phi) - A_{\text{ref}})^2 \rightarrow \min,$$

where $A_{\text{ref}} \in \mathbb{R}^+$ denotes the desired mean area. By using Eq (1.1), we compute the first variation

$$\delta F(\Phi, h) = -2(A(\Phi) - A_{\text{ref}}) \int_0^{L(\Phi)} \langle h, \vec{n}_{\text{inw}} \rangle ds,$$

which decreases most rapidly for $h = \frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial t} = -2(A(\Phi) - A_{\text{ref}}) \vec{n}_{\text{inw}}$ with rate

$$\frac{\partial F}{\partial t} = -2(A(\Phi) - A_{\text{ref}}) L(\Phi).$$

Noteworthy, this gradient flow affects the contour in normal direction only. However, we recommend the use of the AAF from the main article because of its shape-preserving property.

Area-preserving curve-shortening flow. We remind that the area-preserving curve-shortening flow (APCSF) of a contour Φ is given by

$$\frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial t} = \left(\kappa - \frac{2\pi}{L(\Phi)} \right) \vec{n}_{\text{inw}}.$$

By inserting $h = \frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial h}$ into Eq (1.1), we can show that the APCSF is indeed area-preserving:

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial A(\Phi)}{\partial t} &= - \int_0^{L(\Phi)} \langle h, \vec{n}_{\text{inw}} \rangle ds \\
&= - \int_0^{L(\Phi)} \left(\kappa - \frac{2\pi}{L(\Phi)} \right) \|\vec{n}_{\text{inw}}\|_2^2 ds \\
&= - \int_0^{L(\Phi)} \left(\kappa - \frac{2\pi}{L(\Phi)} \right) ds \\
&= - \int_0^{L(\Phi)} \kappa ds + \int_0^{L(\Phi)} \frac{2\pi}{L(\Phi)} ds \\
&= -2\pi + L(\Phi) \frac{2\pi}{L(\Phi)} = 0.
\end{aligned}$$

Furthermore, we can compute the decay of $L(\Phi)$ under the APCSF via:

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial L(\Phi)}{\partial t} &= - \int_0^{L(\Phi)} \frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial t} \cdot \kappa \vec{n}_{\text{inw}} ds \\
&= - \int_0^{L(\Phi)} \left(\kappa - \frac{2\pi}{L(\Phi)} \right) \vec{n}_{\text{inw}} \cdot \kappa \vec{n}_{\text{inw}} ds \\
&= - \int_0^{L(\Phi)} \left(\kappa^2 - \kappa \frac{2\pi}{L(\Phi)} \right) \|\vec{n}_{\text{inw}}\|_2^2 ds \\
&= - \int_0^{L(\Phi)} \kappa^2 ds + \frac{2\pi}{L(\Phi)} \int_0^{L(\Phi)} \kappa ds \\
&= - \int_0^{L(\Phi)} \kappa^2 ds + \frac{4\pi^2}{L(\Phi)}
\end{aligned}$$

Furthermore, the following equality holds:

$$\begin{aligned}
- \int_0^{L(\Phi)} \left(\kappa - \frac{2\pi}{L(\Phi)} \right)^2 ds &= - \int_0^{L(\Phi)} \kappa^2 - \frac{4\pi}{L(\Phi)} \kappa + \frac{4\pi^2}{L(\Phi)^2} ds \\
&= - \int_0^{L(\Phi)} \kappa^2 ds + \frac{8\pi^2}{L(\Phi)} - \frac{4\pi^2}{L(\Phi)} \\
&= - \int_0^{L(\Phi)} \kappa^2 ds + \frac{4\pi^2}{L(\Phi)}
\end{aligned}$$

Then, we can show that the APCSF is indeed an arc length shortening flow:

$$\frac{\partial L(\Phi)}{\partial t} = - \int_0^{L(\Phi)} \left(\kappa - \frac{2\pi}{L(\Phi)} \right)^2 ds \leq 0,$$

with $\frac{\partial L(\Phi)}{\partial t} = 0$ if and only if Φ is a circle with radius $r = \frac{1}{\kappa} = \frac{L}{2\pi}$.

2 Hawkes process: Expected number of offspring

As described in the main paper, the underlying kernel of the Hawkes process is given by $g(t, \theta) = g_1(t) \cdot g_2(\theta)$, separated into a temporal component $g_1(t)$ and a spatial component $g_2(\theta)$. In this context, the temporal kernel is given by

$$g_1(t) = \alpha\beta t e^{-\beta t},$$

with arrival intensity $\alpha > 0$ and exponential decay rate $\beta > 0$. Furthermore, the spatial kernel is defined as the von Mises distribution

$$g_2(\theta) = \frac{e^{\kappa_M \cos(\theta)}}{2\pi I_0(\kappa_M)},$$

with $\kappa_M > 0$ as concentration parameter and $I_0(\kappa_M)$ denoting the modified Bessel function of order 0.

The expected number of offspring under this Hawkes process is then given by the following integral

$$m = \int_0^{2\pi} \int_0^\infty g(t, \theta) dt d\theta$$

Since g_1 and g_2 are continuous and, therefore, g as well, we can use Fubini's theorem. Furthermore, due to g_2 being a probability density function, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} m &= \int_0^{2\pi} g_2(\theta) d\theta \cdot \int_0^\infty g_1(t) dt \\ &= 1 \cdot \int_0^\infty \alpha\beta t e^{-\beta t} dt \\ &= \left[-\frac{\alpha e^{-\beta t} (\beta t + 1)}{\beta} \right]_0^\infty \\ &= \frac{\alpha}{\beta} \end{aligned}$$

For the parameters $\alpha = 0.5s^{-1}$ and $\beta = 0.4s^{-1}$ used in our paper, we obtain the expected number of offspring $m = 0.8$. Given a background intensity $\lambda_0 = 1s^{-1}$ and a time span $T = 500s$, we can compute the expected number of events

$$\lambda_0 \cdot T \cdot \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} m^k = 2500.$$

Therefore, to obtain the same amount of events with a Poisson process, i.e. with one generation of events only, the background intensity must be set to $\lambda_0 = 5s^{-1}$.

3 Estimation of model weights

In this section, we describe our approach how to estimate the model weights w_{prot} , w_{APCSF} , and w_{AAF} when replicating experimental cell tracks with our model.

In this context, we will make use of the local motion kymograph derived from the experimental contour dynamics; see [3] for more details. More precisely, we tune f_{APCSF} and f_{AAF} such that negative regions (i.e. retractions) of the local motion are mainly captured by the above components. For this reason, we introduce the residuals $r_{k,i}$ defined by

$$\begin{aligned} r_{k,i} &= \text{LM}_{k,i} - f_{\text{APCSF}}(t_k, \theta_i) - f_{\text{AAF}}(t_k, \theta_i) \\ &\approx f_{\text{prot}}(t_k, \theta_i) \end{aligned}$$

with local motion $\text{LM}_{k,i}$ at time t_k and virtual marker θ_i .

First, we propose the following two sums of squared residuals

$$\begin{aligned} S &:= \sum_{k,i: \text{LM}_{k,i} < 0} r_{k,i}^2, \\ S^+ &:= \sum_{k,i: \text{LM}_{k,i} < 0} (\min(r_{k,i}, 0))^2. \end{aligned}$$

We are now interested in the pair of retraction weights $w_{\text{retr}} = (w_{\text{APCSF}}, w_{\text{AAF}}) \in \mathbb{R}^2$ which minimizes one of the above sums

$$\min_{w_{\text{retr}} \in \mathbb{R}^2} S \quad \text{or} \quad \min_{w_{\text{retr}} \in \mathbb{R}^2} S^+.$$

While the first case enforces ideally small corrections $r_{k,i}$, the second case favors a positive protrusion component f_{prot} .

Subsequently, after estimating w_{APCSF} and w_{AAF} , we can determine w_{prot} such that the underlying protrusion process

$$X_{\text{prot}}(t_k, \theta_i) = L(t_k) \frac{f_{\text{prot}}(t_k, \theta_i)}{w_{\text{prot}}}$$

fulfills $\text{Var}(X_{\text{prot}}) = 1$ with $\text{Var}(\cdot)$ denoting the sample variance. This can be achieved by choosing

$$w_{\text{prot}} = \sqrt{\text{Var}(\tilde{X}_{\text{prot}})},$$

with

$$\tilde{X}_{\text{prot}}(t_k, \theta_i) := L(t_k) f_{\text{prot}}(t_k, \theta_i).$$

4 Numerical implementation of contour dynamics models

Here, we describe how a contour at time t_k can be evolved for a short time period of $[t_k, t_{k+1}]$. For an initial contour Γ_k , we start with a (preferably) equidistant set of $M \in \mathbb{N}$ contour grid points.

Further, we introduce the following vectorized notation for the spatial coordinates of these markers:

$$\begin{aligned}\Phi_k^{(x)} : [t_k, t_{k+1}] &\rightarrow \mathbb{R}^M, & t &\mapsto \Phi_k^{(x)}(t), \\ \Phi_k^{(y)} : [t_k, t_{k+1}] &\rightarrow \mathbb{R}^M, & t &\mapsto \Phi_k^{(y)}(t), \\ \mathbf{z}_k : [t_k, t_{k+1}] &\rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{2M}, & t &\mapsto \mathbf{z}_k(t) := \begin{bmatrix} \Phi_k^{(x)}(t) \\ \Phi_k^{(y)}(t) \end{bmatrix},\end{aligned}$$

with corresponding center of mass trajectories $\Phi_{\text{CM}}^{(x)}(t), \Phi_{\text{CM}}^{(y)}(t) \in \mathbb{R}$. Moreover, we introduce the following vectorized notations for

- the protrusion process $\mathbf{X}_k^{\text{prot}} \in \mathbb{R}^M$ being constant for the entire time period $[t_k, t_{k+1}]$,
- the contour curvature $\boldsymbol{\kappa}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^M$,
- and the unit normal vector components $\vec{\mathbf{n}}^{(x)}(t), \vec{\mathbf{n}}^{(y)}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^M$.

Then, the vectorized model components $\mathbf{f}, \mathbf{f}_{\text{prot}}, \mathbf{f}_{\text{APCSF}}, \mathbf{f}_{\text{AAF}} : \mathbb{R}^+ \times \mathbb{R}^{2M} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^M$ are given by

$$\begin{aligned}\mathbf{f}_{\text{prot}}(t, \mathbf{z}_k) &= \frac{w_{\text{prot}}}{L(t)} \mathbf{X}_k^{\text{prot}}, \\ \mathbf{f}_{\text{APCSF}}(t, \mathbf{z}_k) &= -w_{\text{APCSF}} \left(\boldsymbol{\kappa}(t) - \frac{2\pi}{L(t)} \mathbb{1}_M \right), \\ \mathbf{f}_{\text{AAF}}(t, \mathbf{z}_k) &= -w_{\text{AAF}} \frac{A(t) - A_{\text{ref}}}{A_{\text{ref}} \cdot L(t)} \left(\left(\Phi^{(x)}(t) - \Phi_{\text{CM}}^{(x)}(t) \mathbb{1}_M \right) \circ \vec{\mathbf{n}}^{(x)}(t) \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \left(\Phi^{(y)}(t) - \Phi_{\text{CM}}^{(y)}(t) \mathbb{1}_M \right) \circ \vec{\mathbf{n}}^{(y)}(t) \right).\end{aligned}$$

In this context, \circ denotes the element-wise (so-called Hadamard) product and $\mathbb{1}_M$ the all-ones vector of dimension M . Now, we can rewrite Eqs. (14) and (15) of the main manuscript for a set of M contour grid points

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{\partial \mathbf{z}_k(t)}{\partial t} &= \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{f}(t, \mathbf{z}_k(t)) \circ \vec{\mathbf{n}}^{(x)}(t) \\ \mathbf{f}(t, \mathbf{z}_k(t)) \circ \vec{\mathbf{n}}^{(y)}(t) \end{bmatrix} \\ \mathbf{f}(t, \mathbf{z}_k(t)) &= \mathbf{f}_{\text{prot}}(t, \mathbf{z}_k(t)) + \mathbf{f}_{\text{APCSF}}(t, \mathbf{z}_k(t)) + \mathbf{f}_{\text{AAF}}(t, \mathbf{z}_k(t)).\end{aligned}\tag{4.1}$$

Given an initial contour Γ_k with equidistant contour grid points with corresponding coordinates $\mathbf{z}_k(t_k) = [\Phi_k^{(x)}(t_k), \Phi_k^{(y)}(t_k)] \in \mathbb{R}^{2M}$, we can now compute the contour dynamics for the time interval $[t_k, t_{k+1}]$ by solving the initial value problem in Eq (4.1). For this purpose, we use the built-in LSODA solver in the Python package SciPy. This solver is based on backward differentiation formulas (BDF) – an implicit method developed to solve especially stiff ordinary differential equations, see [4, 5] for more details. The BDF method of order 1 is better known as implicit Euler method – in our notation given by the formula:

$$\mathbf{z}_k(\tau_{i+1}) = \mathbf{z}_k(\tau_i) + h \cdot \mathbf{f}_k(\tau_{i+1}, \mathbf{z}_k(\tau_{i+1})),$$

with initial time $\tau_0 = t_k$, evaluation times $\tau_i = \tau_0 + ih$ and $\tau_N = t_{k+1}$, step size $h = \frac{\delta t}{N}$, and number of steps $N \in \mathbb{N}$. Whereas, $\mathbf{X}_k^{\text{prot}}$ is set to be constant for the above time integration, the geometric quantities $L(\tau)$, $A(\tau)$, $\kappa(\tau)$, $\vec{\mathbf{n}}(\tau)$, and $\Phi_{\text{CM}}(\tau)$ can be updated for each iteration step $t_k \leq \tau \leq t_{k+1}$ until the coordinates $\mathbf{z}_k(\tau_N) = \mathbf{z}_k(t_{k+1})$ of the consecutive contour Γ_{k+1} are derived.

Finally, we conclude the contour evolution with a contour mapping step, i.e., we compute trajectories of all virtual markers between Γ_k and Γ_{k+1} based on a regularized flow, see Fig 1 and S1 Fig for more details. Afterwards, we proceed with the contour evolution for the next time period $[t_{k+1}, t_{k+2}]$, starting again with a preferably equidistant set of contour grid points.

Regularized flows to counteract VM thinning and clustering. Since the model components from Eq (4.1) are mostly acting in normal direction, thinning and clustering effects of virtual markers are inevitable for longer time periods at the front and rear, respectively. For this reason, we proposed to propagate an equidistant set of contour grid points with respect to Eq (4.1) for a short time interval $[t_k, t_{k+1}]$ only. Afterwards, we map the initial contour at time t_k to the next one at time $t_{k+1} = t_k + \delta t$ based on a regularized flow as described in [3]. In this context, the extent of the regularization of ϕ_k is controlled by a single parameter $\lambda_{\text{reg}} \geq 0$.

In S1 Fig, we illustrate the two different kinds of marker trajectories: (1) the contour propagation based (green dashed lines) and (2) the contour mapping (blue dashed lines) under which X_{prot} is transported. By comparing both trajectories, we can nicely see the necessity to have a certain kind of regularization under which X_{prot} is transported without thinning/clustering effects. Moreover, we use this contour mapping for the underlying spatio-temporal coordinate system of the kymograph descriptions displayed later on. More precisely, horizontal lines of any later shown kymograph describe the corresponding quantity along the regularized VM trajectories.

In 1, we summarized the above algorithm in form of a pseudocode.

Algorithm 1: ContourDynamicsModel

```
Input:  $\Gamma_0, \delta t > 0, \lambda_{\text{reg}} \gg 0, \vartheta_{\text{model}} \in \mathbb{R}^4, \vartheta_{\text{prot}} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_{\text{prot}}}$ 
Output:  $\Gamma_0, \dots, \Gamma_{K-1}$ 

/* Generate protrusion process for the entire time span */
 $X_0^{\text{prot}}, \dots, X_{K-2}^{\text{prot}} = \text{StochasticProcess}(\vartheta_{\text{prot}});$ 

for  $k = 0$  to  $K - 2$  do
    /* Compute virtual marker distance rate */
     $\text{VMDR} = \text{VMDistanceRate}(\Gamma_k);$ 

    /* Adjust protrusion process w.r.t VMDR */
     $X_k^{\text{prot}} = X_k^{\text{prot}} / \text{VMDR};$ 

    /* Compute coordinates of equidistant contour grid points */
     $p_{\text{init}} = \text{GaussianProcessRegression}(\Gamma_k);$ 

    /* Propagate contour grid points based on model functions */
     $p_{\text{end}} = \text{SolveIVP}(p_{\text{init}}, \delta t, X_k^{\text{prot}}, \vartheta_{\text{model}});$ 

    /* Compute contour mapping based on regularized flow */
     $\Gamma_{k+1} = \text{RegularizedFlow}(\Gamma_k, p_{\text{end}}, \lambda_{\text{reg}});$ 
end
return  $\Gamma_0, \dots, \Gamma_{K-1}$ 
```

Figure 1. Algorithm to perform contour dynamics model. The algorithm input consists of an initial contour Γ_0 , a step width $\delta t > 0$, a regularization parameter λ_{reg} , the model parameters $\vartheta_{\text{model}} = \{w_{\text{prot}}, w_{\text{APCSF}}, w_{\text{AAF}}, A_{\text{ref}}\}$, and a set of n_{prot} parameters regarding the stochastic protrusion process denoted with $\vartheta_{\text{prot}} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_{\text{prot}}}$. The output contains the artificial cell track based on consecutive contours $\Gamma_0, \dots, \Gamma_{K-1}$.

5 Model equations with relative weights

In Eq (16) of the main article, our model is notated with absolute weights $w_{\text{prot}}, w_{\text{APCSF}}, w_{\text{AAF}} > 0$. Alternatively, with an overall velocity parameter

$$w_f = w_{\text{prot}} + w_{\text{APCSF}} + w_{\text{AAF}} \cdot 1\mu m$$

our model can be notated via relative weights:

$$\begin{aligned} r_{\text{prot}} &= \frac{w_{\text{prot}}}{w_f}, \\ r_{\text{APCSF}} &= \frac{w_{\text{APCSF}}}{w_f}, \\ r_{\text{AAF}} &= \frac{w_{\text{AAF}} \cdot 1\mu m}{w_f} = (1 - r_{\text{prot}} - r_{\text{APCSF}}). \end{aligned}$$

Then, we can rewrite Eq (15) and Eq (16) of the main article as

$$f = w_f \cdot (f_{\text{prot}} + f_{\text{APCSF}} + f_{\text{AAF}}),$$

with the following three components:

$$\begin{aligned} I : \quad f_{\text{prot}}(t, \theta) &= r_{\text{prot}} \frac{X_{\text{prot}}(t, \theta)}{L(t)} \\ II : \quad f_{\text{APCSF}}(t, \theta) &= r_{\text{APCSF}} \left(\frac{2\pi}{L(t)} - \kappa(t, \theta) \right), \\ III : \quad f_{\text{AAF}}(t, \theta) &= (1 - r_{\text{prot}} - r_{\text{APCSF}}) \frac{A(t) - A_{\text{ref}}}{A_{\text{ref}} \cdot L(t)} \langle \Phi(t, \theta) - \Phi_{\text{CM}}(t), \vec{n}(t, \theta) \rangle. \end{aligned}$$

6 Ornstein-Uhlenbeck process as protrusion process

In this section, we define the protrusion process in our model as diffusion process, more precisely as an Ornstein-Uhlenbeck process which is denoted by

$$X : [0, T] \times [0, 2\pi) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}, \quad (t, \theta) \mapsto X(t, \theta).$$

Further, we introduce the notation for discrete time steps

$$X(k\delta t, \theta) = X(t_k, \theta) = X_k(\theta),$$

with $X(0, \theta) = X_0(\theta) = 0$ for all $\theta \in [0, 2\pi)$.

In the following, we introduce several functions underlying our Ornstein-Uhlenbeck process. Afterwards, we present the exact definition of X .

Scaling functions. An Ornstein-Uhlenbeck process consists of a mean reversion term, preventing the process from getting too small and too large, and a diffusion term, resulting in process changes due to stochastic innovations. For both terms, we introduce the following scaling functions respectively:

- Mean reversion rate function:

$$a : [0, T] \times [0, 2\pi) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+ \text{ with } a_k(\theta) := a(t_k, \theta), \quad (6.1)$$

- Diffusion rate function:

$$b : [0, T] \times [0, 2\pi) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+ \text{ with } b_k(\theta) := b(t_k, \theta). \quad (6.2)$$

Innovation function. As underlying correlation function, from which we draw innovations, we use the normalized Poisson kernel:

$$\tilde{k}_r(\theta, \theta') = \frac{k_r(\theta, \theta')}{\sqrt{k_r(\theta, \theta)k_r(\theta', \theta')}} = \frac{(1-r)^2}{1 - 2r \cos(\theta - \theta') + r^2} \quad (6.3)$$

with $\theta, \theta' \in [0, 2\pi)$, $r \in [0, 1)$. It holds the following properties: $\left(\frac{1-r}{1+r}\right)^2 \leq \tilde{k}_r(\theta, \theta') < 1$ for all $\theta \neq \theta'$ and $\tilde{k}_r(\theta, \theta') = 1$ if and only if $\theta = \theta'$. In S2 Fig, the Poisson kernel function from Eq (1) and its normalized version from Eq (6.3) are shown for different parameters $r \in [0, 1)$.

Then, the innovations of the Ornstein-Uhlenbeck process are denoted by η and are realized by the following Gaussian process:

$$\begin{aligned} \eta : [0, T] \times [0, 2\pi) &\rightarrow \mathbb{R}, \\ (t, \theta) &\mapsto \eta_t(\theta), \\ (\eta)_t &\sim \mathcal{GP}(0, \tilde{k}_{r_{\text{inn}}}(\cdot, \cdot)), \end{aligned}$$

with zero mean and covariance function $\tilde{k}_{r_{\text{inn}}}(\cdot, \cdot)$ from Eq (6.3) and innovation bandwidth parameter $r_{\text{inn}} \in (0, 1)$. For the discrete-time case, we define similarly

$$\eta_k(\theta) := \eta(t_k, \theta) \quad (6.4)$$

By choosing a normalized Poisson kernel as covariance function, we obtain spatially correlated noise, while not affecting the overall variance of X_k . In this context, we use the property that $\tilde{k}_{\text{inn}}(\theta, \theta) = 1$ for all $\theta \in [0, 2\pi)$.

Discrete formulation. Now, we present a time-discrete formula in order to generate an Ornstein-Uhlenbeck process containing the functions from Eq (6.1), (6.2), and (6.4). Again, we will choose a Lagrangian reference frame to describe the process X_k . For a virtual marker labeled by an initial (normalized) arc length coordinate $\theta \in [0, 2\pi)$, the evolution of the protrusion process along this virtual marker is given by $X_k(\theta)$ and starts at $X_0(\theta) = 0$. More precisely, X_k is defined iteratively by the following Ornstein-Uhlenbeck process:

$$\begin{aligned} X_{k+1}(\theta) &= X_k(\theta) + \delta t \cdot \Delta X_k(\theta), \\ \Delta X_k(\theta) &= -a_k(\theta) \cdot X_k(\theta) + \sqrt{2a_k(\theta)} \cdot b_k(\theta) \cdot \eta_k(\theta). \end{aligned} \quad (6.5)$$

In the following, we will use a simplified version with constant rates $a_k(\theta) = a \in \mathbb{R}^+$ and $b_k(\theta) = b \in \mathbb{R}^+$:

$$\Delta X_k(\theta) = -a \cdot X_k(\theta) + \sqrt{2a} \cdot b \cdot \eta_k(\theta). \quad (6.6)$$

Since the magnitude of X_k can be also adjusted by the protrusion weight w_{prot} later on, we recommend to set $b = 1$. This way, and by choosing the normalized Poisson kernel as covariance function of η_k , we obtain $X_k \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 1)$.

Polarization function. A cell polarization can be easily added to the model. This polarization can be induced, e.g., by an extracellular nutrient gradient or by a “master process” defining the general tendency of the cell to move persistently in one direction. We assume that the polarization of the cell is time-dependent and defined by a singular location on the cell contour representing the center of the cell front side. From these assumptions, we introduce the following function

$$\theta_{\text{pol}} : [0, T] \rightarrow [0, 2\pi), \quad t \mapsto \theta_{\text{pol}}(t).$$

A simple test case for a constant polarization would be to choose $\theta_{\text{pol}}(\cdot) = \pi$ as we did for Hawkes processes in the main manuscript.

Further, we define the polarization function $p(t, \theta)$ as the following mapping:

$$p : [0, T] \times [0, 2\pi) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+ \text{ with} \\ (t, \theta) \mapsto \tilde{k}_{r_{\text{pol}}}(\theta, \theta_{\text{pol}}(t)),$$

with normalized Poisson kernel $\tilde{k}_{r_{\text{pol}}}$ defined as in Eq (6.3) with corresponding polarization parameter $r_{\text{pol}} \in [0, 1)$. The polarization function fulfills the property $\left(\frac{1-r_{\text{pol}}}{1+r_{\text{pol}}}\right)^2 \leq p_k(\theta) \leq 1$ and reaches its maximum $p_k(\theta) = 1$ if and only if $\theta = \theta_{\text{pol}}(t_k)$, for more details see S2 Fig.

For the case $r_{\text{pol}} = 0$ and any function $\theta_{\text{pol}} : [0, T] \rightarrow [0, 2\pi)$, the polarization function simplifies to

$$p(\cdot, \cdot) = \tilde{k}_0(\cdot, \theta_{\text{pol}}(\cdot)) = 1,$$

i.e., no polarization effect takes place. For the case $r_{\text{pol}} \rightarrow 1$, the polarization functions simplifies to

$$p(t, \theta) = \begin{cases} 1, & \theta = \theta_{\text{pol}}(t) \\ 0, & \theta \neq \theta_{\text{pol}}(t) \end{cases}$$

which is equal to the indicator function $\mathbb{1}_{\{\theta_{\text{pol}}(t)\}}(\theta)$. Finally, we introduce a discrete notation:

$$p_k(\theta) := p(t_k, \theta) = \tilde{k}_{r_{\text{pol}}}(\theta, \theta_{\text{pol}}(t_k)). \quad (6.7)$$

Protrusion component. Motivated from the biological insight that protrusions and retractions are triggered by the underlying actin and myosin concentration, respectively, we designed our model to separate the formation of protrusions from the formation of retractions. However, in order to obtain a separation of protrusions, resulting from the protrusion component, and retractions, resulting from the APCSF and AAF, the process $X(t, \theta)$

should only take positive values. For this reason, we propose the following modifications of the Ornstein-Uhlenbeck process from Eq (6.5):

$$\begin{aligned}
X_{\text{prot}}^+(t_k, \theta) &:= \frac{p_k(\theta)}{\text{VMDR}(t_k, \theta)} \cdot X_k(\theta)^+, \\
X_{\text{prot}}^2(t_k, \theta) &:= \frac{p_k(\theta)}{\text{VMDR}(t_k, \theta)} \cdot X_k(\theta)^2, \\
X_{\text{prot}}^{\text{exp}}(t_k, \theta) &:= \frac{p_k(\theta)}{\text{VMDR}(t_k, \theta)} \cdot \exp(X_k(\theta)), \\
X_{\text{prot}}^{\text{lin}}(t_k, \theta) &:= \frac{p_k(\theta)}{\text{VMDR}(t_k, \theta)} \cdot X_k(\theta) + c_{\text{lin}} \\
X_{\text{prot}}^{\text{log}}(t_k, \theta) &:= \frac{p_k(\theta)}{\text{VMDR}(t_k, \theta)} \cdot \frac{1}{1 + \exp(-\beta_{\text{log}} X_k(\theta))},
\end{aligned} \tag{6.8}$$

with $c_{\text{lin}} > 0$, $\beta_{\text{log}} > 0$, and polarization function p_k defined as in Eq (6.7) and virtual marker distance ratio defined as in Eq (4) in the main article. In the case of the linear modification, $c_{\text{lin}} > 0$ needs to be sufficiently large in order to obtain mostly positive values for $X_{\text{prot}}^{\text{lin}}$.

Simulating amoeboid motility by an Ornstein-Uhlenbeck process

In the main manuscript, we have shown that amoeboid cell motility can be well simulated with a self-exciting Poisson point process, as so-called Hawkes process. In this section, we want to investigate whether such a self-exciting property is necessary to produce realistic contour dynamics. For this reason, we simulated contour dynamics driven by an Ornstein-Uhlenbeck process (OUP) defined as in Eq (6.6). The OUP is widely used in other cell motility models where it is often used to model changes of two-dimensional bio marker concentrations. For this reason, we investigated if the OUP is also suitable within our model. In the above section, we introduced multiple modifications of the OUP, necessary to separate the formation of protrusions from the formation of retractions. We therefore studied the influence of each modification on the overall contour dynamics.

First, we generated cell tracks based on the OUP in Eq (6.6) for all modifications mentioned above. In this context, the mean reversion rate and diffusion rate were set to be constant: $a = 0.05$ and $b = 1$. Furthermore, we assumed no polarization, i.e., $r_{\text{pol}} = 0$. Since the modifications from Eq (6.8) affect the magnitude of the protrusion process in different ways, the protrusion weight w_{prot} needed to be adjusted for each modification. For this reason, we have chosen $w_{\text{prot}} = 15; 5; 5; 7.5; 20$ for X_{prot}^+ , X_{prot}^2 , $X_{\text{prot}}^{\text{exp}}$, $X_{\text{prot}}^{\text{lin}}$, and $X_{\text{prot}}^{\text{log}}$, respectively. In general, the reference area of A_{ref} acts as lower bound of the area in our model. From experimental recordings, we can say that $A_{\text{ref}} = 80\mu\text{m}^2$ is plausible for an exemplary cell track. The exact choice

of all parameters can be found in Table 1. The first group of parameters regarding the contour parametrization and the flow between contours is described in a more detailed way in [3].

Table 1. Choice of parameters and meaning.

Parameter	Value	Unit	Meaning
Contour parametrization			
r_{cont}	0.6	–	GPR smoothing
σ_{noise}	0.05	–	GPR noise
λ_{reg}	10	$\frac{\mu\text{m}^2}{\text{s}^2}$	Flow regularization
A_{ref}	80	μm^2	Reference area
Ornstein-Uhlenbeck process			
a	0.05	s^{-1}	Mean reversion rate
b	1	$\text{s}^{-\frac{1}{2}}$	Diffusion rate
r_{inn}	0.5	–	Corr. length of innovations
r_{pol}	0	–	Corr. length of polarization
Model weights			
w_{prot}	5–20	$\frac{\mu\text{m}}{\text{s}}$	Protrusion weight
w_{APCSF}	0.1	$\frac{\mu\text{m}}{\text{s}}$	APCSF weight
w_{AAF}	1	$\frac{\mu\text{m}}{\text{s}}$	AAF weight

List of parameters for artificial cell tracks based on an Ornstein-Uhlenbeck process.

In the top row of Fig 2, cell tracks based on the different modifications from Eq (6.8) are shown. For each modification, the same realization of the Ornstein-Uhlenbeck process X_{prot} is underlying. The non-polarized behavior of the cell tracks can be clearly seen. From the covered trace (grey area) of each cell track and its corresponding center of mass trajectory (colored line), we observe different degrees of motility for $X_{\text{prot}}^{\text{exp}}$, X_{prot}^+ , X_{prot}^2 , $X_{\text{prot}}^{\text{lin}}$, and $X_{\text{prot}}^{\text{log}}$ (descending order).

Furthermore, the kymographs of the overall local motion f and its three components f_{prot} , f_{APCSF} , f_{AAF} are displayed for each of these cell tracks. For X_{prot}^+ , the expanding regions (red, first two columns) are more distinct and with sharp edges directly resulting from the non-smooth behavior of X_{prot}^+ . In contrast, the expanding regions of X_{prot}^2 are smoother. Furthermore, by taking also the negative parts of X_{prot} into account, the number of expanding regions approximately doubles. For the third case $X_{\text{prot}}^{\text{exp}}$, we observe kymographs similar to X_{prot}^+ but with smoother transitions between expansions and

Figure 2. Comparison of cell tracks obtained from different modifications of the underlying Ornstein-Uhlenbeck process. In the first row, the entire area (trace) covered by each cell track is displayed (left, gray area) as well as their center of mass trajectories (left, colored lines) and the evolution of the contour dynamics over a time span of $T = 500s$ (right, colored contours). Below, for each modification, the corresponding kymographs of the following quantities are displayed for the first half of each cell track: the local motion f and its three components f_{prot} , f_{APCSF} , and f_{AAF} (from left to right).

retractions. In the fourth case, we have chosen $c_{\text{lin}} = 1.96$ such that $\mathbb{P}(X_{\text{prot}}^{\text{lin}} > 0) = 0.975$. As a consequence of this mean shift, the corresponding protrusion kymograph shows larger expanding regions. Due to a larger protrusion component, the size of the cell contour is significantly increased. Since f_{APCSF} is proportional to the contour curvature, the corresponding kymograph (3rd column) becomes more even if the contour size increases. An increased contour area can be also inferred from the f_{AAF} kymograph (4th column), which is characterized by a darker blue, leading to a stronger area adjustment. For the logistic modification $X_{\text{prot}}^{\text{log}}$ with $\beta_{\text{log}} = 2$, a similar effect of an increased contour size can be observed.

In S3 Vid, all five cell tracks are displayed at tenfold speed. In accordance to the kymographs from Fig 2, we observed the non-smooth behavior for X_{prot}^+ with abrupt changes of the cell contour. For X_{prot}^2 , we observed more protrusions evolving more smoothly compared to X_{prot}^+ . However, by creating

too many protrusions, canceling each other out, the overall cell motility can be reduced, which was previously studied for example in [6]. Since X_{prot}^2 depends also on the negative regions of the initial Ornstein-Uhlenbeck process, the resulting cell track differs significantly from the other four cell tracks, which are synchronous most of the time. From the exponential modification $X_{\text{prot}}^{\text{exp}}$, a cell track with rapidly generated protrusions was observed. Finally, the cell tracks obtained from $X_{\text{prot}}^{\text{lin}}$ and $X_{\text{prot}}^{\text{log}}$ were almost stationary with an increased cell shape and lesser curvature which coincides with the above observations.

In general, we recommend using the exponential modification $X_{\text{prot}}^{\text{exp}}$ resulting in smooth contour changes driven by fast and more explorative protrusions. However, some protrusions look artificial as well as additional artifacts such as a pulsating membrane and a partially swimming type of locomotion. While this method provides a simple way of generating cell tracks, they can be easily distinguished from experimental cell tracks. Based on the findings of the main article, by choosing the Hawkes process as underlying protrusion component, much more realistic contour dynamics can be generated. Due to its self-exciting property, the Hawkes process is capable of producing cascades of multiple protrusions with accompanying reorientation phases of the cell. Compared to the OUP, the Hawkes process is therefore much more advantageous.

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